

Introduction: The acquisition of multiple spectral bands is clearly beneficial for solar system exploration missions, enabling the detection of mineralogical component signatures. Ideally, a spectro-imager would allow hyperspectral acquisitions, but the constraints of rover missions often necessitate simpler and less bulky solutions. Filter wheels positioned in front of panchromatic cameras are then often used (see for ex. [1]), but they present several drawbacks:

- An increase in acquisition time to cycle through all the filters – this is not a significant issue for rover missions, as the rover and the scene are stationary,
- An increase in the volume of data to be transferred,
- A mechanism that introduces a potential point of failure and additional mass.

Currently, cameras with Multi-Spectral Filter Arrays (MSFA) are being developed. These are an extension of Color Filter Arrays (CFA) (like the Bayer pattern), with patterns typically of 4x4 or 5x5 pixels. Such sensors, with the scientific objective to distinguish spectrally between mineralogic features on the Moon, will be onboard the lunar mission Rashid-3 by the Mohammed Bin Rashid Space Centre (MBRSC), with a launch scheduled not earlier than 2029 [2]. One is a 25-bands camera (CAM-25, Fig.1) and the other is an 8-bands camera including panchromatic pixels (CAM-8, Fig.6). Sensors with SWIR capabilities are also under development for future missions.

Fig 1: CAM-25 pattern and filters (wavelengths in nm)

Demosaicing Principle: The images acquired in this manner combine spatial and spectral sampling: they exhibit a form of significant compression, as there is only one image plane (Fig.2) instead of the N planes that one wishes to acquire, but the hyperspectral cube thus formed is very sparse. When spatial resolution is prioritized, demosaicing processing is applied to deduce missing pixels, providing access to the high spatial frequencies of the scene. The processing thus produces high-resolution spatial maps: this is a spatial approach to using mosaicked images.

Fig 2: Three examples of mosaicked images (CAM-25)

Our Demosaicing Method Steps: This method is mostly derived from [3] and was benchmarked in [4] on simulated images with quantitative criteria.

Pseudo-Panchromatic Image. It involves first determining a pseudo-panchromatic image (Fig.3) using ‘‘Local Directional Information’’ (LDI) as detailed in [3], which thus contains the high-frequency information restored from all the normalized spectral bands. The main idea is to take benefit from the variations of the intensity from the 8 adjacent macro-pixels to deduce the intensity for each pixel.

Fig 3: Pseudo-PAN images by LDI (from [4])

Intensity-Difference Demosaicing. Then, for a given spectral band, the principle is to interpolate the intensity differences between the pixels actually sampled for this band and the same pixels in the pseudo-panchromatic image, in order to estimate these differences for the other pixels. The values of the pseudo-panchromatic image and these interpolated differences are used to fill in the missing measurements in the reconstructed spectral image. This approach, applied for all the spectral bands, has led to the best results in terms of fidelity to the source images, in the case of simulations, where the ground truth is known [4].

Iterations by Spectral Difference. It is ultimately possible to complement this processing with iterations based on the ‘‘spectral difference method’’. The principle is similar to the intensity difference, but instead of using the pseudo-panchromatic image, the pixels actually sampled in the other bands are used. The values of the other bands at the pixels actually sampled in the band being reconstructed are calculated by simple weighted bilinear interpolation. Then the differences between the two bands are interpolated, and the values at the pixels from other bands deduced from the measured values and these differences. This interpolation is improved by iterating the process with the results of the previous iterations instead of the pseudo-panchromatic image (Fig.4).

Fig 4: Processed imgs at 716nm (from [4])

Quantitatively, improvements are noted, but they are hardly visually perceptible. Moreover, the computation time increases significantly. By default, these iterations are not activated, but they can be implemented on certain images, primarily to improve spectral rendering.

Results:

Simulated Images. The quantitative and qualitative results presented in [4] show high spatial fidelity of the reconstructed images, illustrated in Fig.5. However, these simulations represent pessimistic cases for this spatial demosaicing, as spectral rejection is assumed to be perfect and crosstalk non-existent: the reality of these effects will make naturally spectral reconstruction more difficult, but on the other hand, spatial reconstruction will be easier, as there will be better continuity of information from one pixel to another, with the spectral filters ultimately being less effective.

Fig 5: Colored compositions with 944/756/663nm bands

Real images. Some images were taken during an experiment in late 2025 in the Atacama desert, known to present good analogues of Lunar and Martian mineralogy [5]. The camera used for the experiment was designed as CAM-8 onboard Rashid-3.

Fig 6: CAM-8 pattern and filters (wavelengths in nm)

We tested this demosaicing algorithm (Fig.8), without trying to take benefit of the panchromatic redundancy, and compared it to a direct bilinear interpolation of the panchromatic pixels (Fig.7).

Fig 7: Zoom on a mosaicked image (left), the panchromatic pixels direct interpolation (middle), the pseudo-panchro. image from this algorithm (right)

The obtained image seems to show a better spatial resolution, maybe a bit more noisy, although we do not know the detailed ground truth in this case.

Fig 8: CAM-8 colored comp. with 769/716/553nm bands

Computation Time. The computational performance was evaluated by comparison with an efficient demosaicing method [6] on simple Bayer images (matrices of 2048x2048 pixels with 3 colors, as for the Rashid-2 rover cameras). The result with a standard PC is a computation time 4.5 times longer (without iterations), which remains very reasonable.

Conclusion: The demosaicing algorithm presented here is based on a spatial approach to process MSFA images. Spectral fidelity is therefore not the primary criterion, but other ongoing studies aim to best exploit the spectral information for geological analysis of rocks and minerals identification [7]. It provides excellent high-resolution spatial quality: there is no need for an additional panchromatic image, as the MSFA image is self-sufficient. Of course, the flux is lower, so the exposure time must be increased compared to a panchromatic camera, but with a single image and no mechanical filter wheel, the spectral richness of the observed scene shall be accessed. The acquisition time is thus globally reduced, as is the data volume, while maintaining a high-resolution image at several wavelengths. This processing will be implemented in the CASPIP library [8] to be used for Rashid-3 mission.

References: [1] Bell J.F., The Mars 2020 Perseverance Rover Mast Camera Zoom (Mastcam-Z) (2017), *Space Sci Rev.* [2] Almatroushi H. et al., Rashid 3 mission: UAE's lunar rover to the South Pole (2026) *ELS.* [3] Mihoubi S. et al., Multispectral Demosaicing using Pseudo-Panchromatic Image (2017), *IEEE TCI, vol. 3.* [4] Renaudeau A. et al., Méthodes de démosaïquage multispectral pour l'imagerie spatiale (2025) *GRETSI (30th).* [5] Flahaut J., et al., Rheology of the Andean Domes as an Analog for Lunar Silicic Constructs (2021), *EGU21-11780. Copernicus Meetings.* [6] Hamilton J. F. and Adams J. J. E. (1997), *USA Patent 5629734.* [7] Fsihan H. et al., Image Sensor Absolute Quantum Efficiency Characterization for Reliable Planetary Mineralogy (2026), *ELS.* [8] Théret N. et al., CASPEX Image Processing: a Tool for Space Exploration (2024), *EPSC, Vol. 17.*